

A Theory of Adaptive Processing: From Confinement to Maneuverability

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Most of human conceptualization and behavior is in large part directed by what can be described as the survival imperative. The need to meet physiological, organismic and ecosystemic demands occupies most if not all our time. The successful regulation of our mental and physical state relies upon a constraint contingent attainment of specific outcomes that are appraised as beneficial. The requirement to overcome obstacles or adversity operates mainly in the context of charting a trajectory that maximizes the acquisition of desirable outcomes. This discussion seeks to suggest that an exclusive outcomes orientation leads more to confinement than to maneuverability and that this confinement might also be viewed as a function of processing that is not optimally adaptive.

Confinement or **insufficiency proneness** is described as the propensity to appraise any given psychophysical state or condition as insufficient or incomplete. **Maneuverability** is the skillful negotiation of insufficiency proneness in order to fashion or access a milieu that is most fulfillment and wellness generating. The confinement-maneuverability continuum shifts emphasis to individual appraisal rather than any inherent nature lying within phenomena.

It is proposed that maneuverability enabling processing has at least three characteristics. That of systemic attention as opposed to fractionated attention, a framework disposition and a mix of both outcomes' orientation as well as process orientation.

Systemic attention is described as a purposeful appreciation of phenomena outside the ambit of immediate processing. This attentional shifting or deselecting is independent of any perceived relevance to what one's present emphasis might be. An example of this might be the inclusion into awareness or more so, an active appreciation of what lies in one's field of vision or a specific sensation arising from the body while being engrossed in a particular line of thought. Systemic attention as opposed to fractionated attention might facilitate the disentanglement from dysfunctional mental phenomena such as excessive worry and rumination or from overpowering emotional states. **Fractionated attention** could be seen as the tendency to attend to and ascribe significance to any one facet of experience such that over time, this circumscription leads to limitations in the perceptual, affective, conative and perhaps even cognitive repertoire that we might access. Systemic attention recognizes the co-arising and inter-relational nature of the reality that we inhabit irrespective of individual narratives and motivations. Systemic attention is much more than mere distraction or wandering. It is the active investing of significance to all possible forms of experience whether any such import is apparent or not. The capacity to be able to confer equal weightage to all forms of experience is a fallout of exercising systemic attention and is likely a skill that can be acquired.

Polarity disposition is the disposition to base intention and behavior on supposedly definite characterization of one or more elements of experience. Being polarity disposed means conferring irrevocability on what is mostly circumstantially derived and often momentary. A **framework disposition** on the other hand recognizes that potential rather than fixed delimitation is foundational for optimal development and movement. With a framework disposition, the arising of potential is seen both as the basis as well as the endpoint of the process of development. Any form of cultivation is aimed at generating further ground for framework building and fixedness is seen to channel into crystallization and not progression. Any fixedness or polarization presents the opportunity for only temporary recourse, and it is the prospect of continual possibility and dynamic unfolding that is the basis for action with a framework disposition. With a polarity disposition, movement ceases upon qualification whereas with a framework disposition, the emphasis is on the structuring of a state of movement. The framework thus forever expands, is adaptive and allows for a greater range of possibilities, much like the fluidity of water allows the incorporation of substances like salt or dye whereas the hardness of ice does not.

While a certain degree of focus on outcomes is desirable and likely necessary, it is suggested that exclusive outcome orientation leads more to what has been described as confinement rather than maneuverability. Being singularly outcome-oriented limits the space which allows adaptivity and openness to emerge because the preoccupation with obtaining a specific outcome directs all effort and action. **Process orientation** attenuates the primacy of reward and drives engagement that is free of dependence on any set of conditions. This leeway provides room for the discovery of avenues for enrichment that might be ignored when driven solely by the need for attaining a goal. In fact, being process oriented allows the identification of goals that are worthwhile. The right mix of outcome and process orientation eases urgency and bestows the capability to compensate for perturbation. Fruition when derived from the process rather than the outcome enhances unconditional regard not only for all varieties of experience but also of the self and others. It is theorized that systemic attention and a framework disposition serve to potentiate the ability to be optimally process oriented.

This model of adaptive processing examines the notion of confinement from a perspective that might enable a considerable degree of freedom despite inevitable constraints. The shift in emphasis from supposed inherent and unchangeable nature to individual measure is more conducive to the development as well as the exercising of capabilities that recruit the very factors that are deemed limiting. The introduction of notions such as systemic attention and framework disposition will hopefully lead to further elucidation of the characteristics of individual appraisal and measure that are amenable to modeling and subsequent modulation. Each of the elements of the model presented allow design of methodologies, techniques and interventions that might aid not only in ameliorating psychopathological states but in advancing the ability to access wellbeing and fulfillment irrespective of circumstantial determinants.

References

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